

in the singularly challenging conditions of economic inequality, warring nation states, and the jealousy of trade. The only Smith who appears in the book is Al Smith, calling FDR un-American in 1936.

Is de Dijn convincing? The argument that early nineteenth-century liberalism was different is well done. At the same time, the portrayal of numerous political actors is wanting. Let's take Richard Price, lauded here as an archetypal democrat and activist for liberty. Yet Price said over and over that liberty could never be established without the abolition of empire and the establishment of perpetual peace. Praising popular government meant nothing unless you got the political economy right. This was why authors who de Dijn would have lauded into the camp of the ancients, such as the leaders of the Genevan revolution of 1782, favored political liberty in small republics, even calling for democracy, but were avowed enemies to events in France.

The view of so many advocates of liberty was that creating strong forms of community through political liberty risked creating fanatic forms of republicanism akin to the Puritanism that had flourished in time of Reformation. The challenge was establishing popular liberty without fanaticism, xenophobia, empire-building, and war, all of the forces that tended to act as social glue in times of crisis. This was why Burke was horrified by a revolution turned republican empire abolishing all of the free republics in the 1790s. If Poland-Lithuania was eaten up by Austria, Russia, and Prussia, it was the First French Republic that put an end to the independence of Geneva, the Swiss Confederation, the Dutch Republic, Genoa, and Venice. Constant was so depressed, having been a revolutionary republican in the 1790s, that the model state for moderns after the Napoleonic Wars had become rapacious Britain. This was why he formulated a moral philosophy tied to polytheism to support his theory of modern liberty. It remains unclear why democratic or republican populism today, however direct in form or egalitarian, could be trusted to avoid Caesar figures, disorder, war, xenophobia, or empire-building. The early nineteenth-century question remains, how does a patriotic people ruling a large and heavily armed commercial state prevent regular descent into fanaticism?

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Cities of Splendour in the Shaping of Sephardi History. By *Jane S. Gerber*. London: Littleman Library of Jewish Civilization, 2020. Pp. xiii+302. \$52.50.

Jane Gerber invites her readers to join her on her travels through time and space. For many years, and with infectious enthusiasm, she has been traversing historical periods and geographical boundaries tirelessly in search of intriguing new insights regarding Sephardi Jewry, a fluid diasporic community that is often connected, as Gerber herself admits, only by a distant memory or a vague family relation, real or imagined, to their country of origin and to its Jewish golden age.

I took my first journey with Jane Gerber through her edited collection, *The Jews of the Caribbean* (London, 2014). Gerber and her colleagues took their readers on a journey in the footsteps of the Jews who lived in this exotic area beginning in the sixteenth century, when Conversos who had fled the inquisitions of the Iberian Peninsula established communities there and later returned to open Judaism, becoming known as "Portuguese" Jews, to World War II, when Jewish refugees arrived in the Caribbean after escaping from the clutches of the Nazis. The book is fascinating and revealed a world that was new to me.

I later read many of Gerber's other fine works, chief among them her comprehensive volume entitled *The Jews of Spain: A History of the Sephardic Experience* (Toronto, 1992).

In her latest book, *Cities of Splendour in the Shaping of Sephardi History*, Gerber examines the story of the Sephardi Jewry by researching their experiences in prominent diasporic cities. She begins with medieval Spain, focusing on Muslim Cordoba and Catholic Toledo. After the expulsion of the Jews from Spain in 1492, she turns to the Sephardi community in Safed in the sixteenth century (with a passage also on Tiberias), Venice in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, Istanbul and Salonika from 1492–1600, and, finally, Amsterdam from the late sixteenth century to 1700, where she examines the establishment of the “Western Sephardi diaspora” by Conversos who escaped the Iberian inquisitions and returned to open Judaism, becoming known as “Portuguese” Jews. Some of them also eventually reached the Caribbean.

Gerber opens the study by challenging the commonly held view in Sephardi Jewish historiography that contrasts the friendly rule of the Muslims to the persecution that characterized Christian rule. Gerber argues that this understanding is simplistic and inaccurate. The lives of the Jews, she claims, depended on the whims of the ruler, the specific area of residence, and political circumstances. Gerber discusses the complex relationship between Jews and the various rulers and argues that even if the Jews were treated more favorably in certain periods under Muslim rule than under Christian rule, it was mainly due to the Muslim rulers' appreciation for their education and language skills. In general, Jews in Spain were weak and vulnerable, and their lives were filled with suffering.

However, one of the main claims of the study is that despite their ongoing persecution and final expulsion, Sephardi Jews continued to look to Spain as a source of pride and longing. According to Gerber, this was because the Jews had lived in Spain for as long as they had lived in the land of Israel, and therefore they considered themselves the direct descendants of the original exiles of ancient Israel. Gerber noted that in the medieval period, the Jews in Spain acquired prestige in the eyes of their Muslim and Christian neighbors by claiming direct lineage to King David and the priests and Levites in the Temple, while the Ashkenazim were considered of less noble descent. This sense of glory did not fade with the passage of time. In January 1790, during the French Revolution, we hear the same claim made by David Silveyra, a “Portuguese” Jew, and the representative of the Sephardi communities of Bayonne and Paris in the French Assemblée Constituante, who requested that the assembly grant the Sephardi Jews in France civil status. In his declaration (*La Révolution française et l'Émancipation des Juifs*, vol. 5 [Paris, 1968], texte 14), Silveyra emphasized the Spanish origin of his community as a source of pride and prestige, directly linking the Jews of Spain to King David and the Temple, and completely overlooking the Sephardi Jews' suffering before the expulsion.

Another central argument of Gerber's research is that due to Spain's distinctive character, Sephardi Jewry was uniquely open to external influences. She argues that the Iberian Peninsula was the only place in Europe where Christians, Muslims, and Jews lived side by side for centuries, creating an exceptional interaction among their cultures that allowed each of these communities to absorb the best of each other's cultures. After the expulsion, Sephardi Jews continued to emphasize the importance of both Jewish and general education in their new places of residence. They were fluent in foreign languages, participated in international trade, and raised generations of influential physicians, scientists, and thinkers. According to Gerber, the dispersal of the Sephardi diaspora around the world, its openness to the outside world, and the wide-ranging influences it has absorbed have transformed it into a global and transnational diaspora in the modern era, when global culture has become a supreme value. For this reason, Gerber claims that Sephardi Jews were the first modern Jews.

One of the single weaknesses of the study is the overly brief discussion devoted to the Converso communities established in France from the second half of the sixteenth century (220–21), despite their important connections with Amsterdam and the Iberian Peninsula, and the paucity of references on the subject. In the few lines she devotes to this question, Gerber refers to David Graizbord's well-known research, but does not mention the work of other prominent scholars such as Carsten Wilke.

In conclusion, this is a refreshing, encompassing, and fascinating study, penned by an experienced and knowledgeable researcher, and supported by a rich bibliography. It offers a new look and an original interpretation of the story of Sephardi Jewry from the medieval period to the eighteenth century. Moreover, the author's flowing prose and the book's careful editing make it a suitable choice for skilled researchers, as well as for students seeking to study the chapters of a long and painful history, but one that is also full of the glory and splendor of one of the most prominent diasporas of the Jewish people.

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State Formation and Shared Sovereignty: The Holy Roman Empire and the Dutch Republic, 1488–1690. By *Christopher W. Close.*

New York: Cambridge University Press, 2021. Pp. xii+370. \$99.99 (cloth); \$80.00 (Adobe eBook Reader).

The early modern state is commonly understood as characterized by sovereignty, centralized government, and bureaucracy. The Holy Roman Empire does not fit these criteria. The emperor was not a sovereign outside his family lands; from ca. 1555 basic functions of government, notably keeping the peace, were entrusted to territorial "Circles"; and Prussian Berlin, not imperial Vienna, developed a model bureaucracy.

Recent scholarship gives a better appreciation of the Empire's federal constitution and how it worked. For example, notwithstanding religious divisions, the imperial Circles raised considerable sums to shore up Habsburg defenses against the Ottomans in Hungary and Croatia, beyond the Empire's frontiers. Meanwhile, Europe's recent habit of setting limits to state sovereignty may have modified expectations of what a proper state should look like.

For Jean Bodin, sovereignty was one and indivisible. But the newer work on German history has shown that divided sovereignty could work reasonably well. Christopher Close alludes to this discussion, presenting state formation in Germany as a case of "shared sovereignty." But he also wishes to extend the argument a bit further.

Of the myriad territorial entities that made up late medieval and early modern Germany, as many as a hundred had the wherewithal to raise at least a small army. Lay and ecclesiastical princes, imperial cities, and important abbeys formed leagues or alliances among themselves, always for the stated purpose of mutual self-defense. Both now and in the past, historical treatment of the leagues has usually shown them as working at cross-purposes to the stability and coherence of the Empire. But Close makes a plausible case that leagues were often a force more for public order than for disruption.

Alliances included smaller states as well as great princes. While princes had ambitious plans, their lesser partners—imperial cities or imperial abbeys—hoped to preserve the status quo. Princes set the agenda, but smaller members paid a good part of the budget and made their voices heard. Thus a league might raise an army but use it sparingly, to